

Measuring Agent Governance Posture: Accountability Gaps in MCP Servers and Implications for Single- and Multi-Agent Governance

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Abstract

Governance frameworks for agentic AI call for identity, authorization, auditability, and human oversight, but these requirements often remain abstract. This study measures whether those controls exist in practice across 945 Model Context Protocol (MCP) servers drawn from a population of 17,563, using deterministic analysis, LLM verification, and human-validated classification. Tools are classified on two axes – read/write and sensitivity – and scanned for seven accountability gap patterns.

We find that 71% of source-available servers exhibit at least one gap (95% CI: [67.6%, 74.0%]). This is a lower bound: the gap construct requires that governance infrastructure be present to be found deficient, so a server with no governance at all exhibits zero gaps and is not flagged. Two patterns lead in near-equal measure: global authentication applied uniformly across tools of differing sensitivity (41%) and authenticated access without actor-attributed logging (40%). An additional 20% of the sample (185 remote-only servers) is fully opaque to assessment.

Drawing on XACML and NIST SP 800-162, we distinguish six governance concerns. Only enforcement and audit are fully observable from source code (policy authoring partially so), and we operationalize these; the remaining three require runtime instrumentation. Two structural findings emerge. The enforcement-audit gap: 81% of servers authenticate callers, but only 17% attribute logged actions to specific principals. The sensitive-read gap: 198 tools across 91 source-available servers expose protected data through read operations that would be invisible to write-focused governance models, and 79% of these servers lack co-located audit logging.

1. Introduction

When a human delegates a task to an AI agent, a structural collapse occurs: the requester, the reasoner, the actor, and the record-keeper merge into a single operational chain. The agent decides which tools to call, executes them with whatever authority it holds, and may produce the only record of what happened. This collapse is not a bug in any particular implementation; rather, it is the default architecture of agentic systems and the structural condition that governance frameworks attempt to address.

Governance frameworks for AI agents have proliferated rapidly. The OWASP Top 10 for Agentic

Applications (2026) identifies risks including unrestricted tool permissions, identity and privilege abuse, and insufficient logging. The OWASP MCP Top 10 (2025) catalogs protocol-specific risks. SAFE-MCP (Linux Foundation/OpenID Foundation) proposes a common security baseline. The NIST AI Agent Standards Initiative (2026) frames a three-pillar approach spanning industry standards, community protocols, and research. Each of these frameworks prescribes controls. None provides ecosystem-scale empirical evidence of whether those controls exist in practice.

This paper addresses that gap. The Model Context Protocol (MCP), developed by Anthropic and adopted by major AI vendors, externalizes tool capabilities at a protocol boundary between client and server. Each MCP server declares tools with names, descriptions, and optional annotations. This boundary creates a point where governance controls become observable: does the server authenticate callers? Does it distinguish read from write operations? Does it log who did what? Does it protect sensitive data access with the same rigor as state-modifying operations?

We measure governance posture across a stratified random sample of 945 MCP servers drawn from the full ecosystem population of 17,563 unique servers enumerated from three canonical registries: the MCP Registry, npm, and PyPI. Using a deterministic-first analysis pipeline with LLM verification and human-validated classification, we extract 14,282 tools, classify them on two orthogonal axes (read/write and sensitivity), scan for seven named accountability gap patterns, and code 11 governance indicators per server.

The study makes three empirical claims:

1. Accountability gaps are prevalent. Among the 760 source-available servers in our sample, 71% exhibit at least one named gap pattern (95% CI: [67.6%, 74.0%]). This figure is a lower bound, because a gap can only be detected where some governance infrastructure exists to be incomplete; servers with no governance at all register zero gaps (Section 6.1). An additional 185 remote-only servers (20% of the sample) are fully opaque to governance assessment, with all indicators coded Indeterminate.
2. Governance-relevant data exposure through read operations is invisible to write-focused governance models. We identify 198 tools that expose protected data – credentials, PII, financial records – without modifying persistent state. Among the 91 source-available servers with such sensitive-read tools, 79% lack co-located audit logging. This is a category of governance risk that read/write classification alone cannot surface.
3. The gap between enforcement and audit is measurable at ecosystem scale. 81% of source-available servers implement some form of authentication, but only 17% implement actor-attributed logging. Servers gate access but cannot prove who did what afterward. This enforcement-audit gap is the central structural finding.

This paper does not propose a new governance framework for AI agents. It measures whether one emerging agent tool ecosystem exposes the minimum implementation evidence needed for governance frameworks to be meaningful.

Relationship to prior work

Stein (2026) provides the closest methodological precedent, classifying 177,000 MCP tools by capability domain (perception, reasoning, action) using LLM-based classification with human validation. Our work is complementary: where Stein maps what agents can do, we map what governance infrastructure exists around what agents do. Our classification axes (read/write and sensitivity) are

oriented toward governance posture rather than capability taxonomy, and our primary contribution is the prevalence measurement of accountability gap patterns rather than capability distribution.

Uchibeke (2026) proposes the Open Agent Passport (OAP) for deterministic pre-action authorization in autonomous AI agents, evaluated against 4,437 adversarial authorization decisions. Our data measures the problem OAP addresses: the prevalence of ungated writes (29%), global authentication over sensitive tools (41%), and the absence of per-tool authorization (95% of servers).

Hahn et al. (2026) provide the ethical framing for agent governance most relevant to the present study’s accountability focus, examining how AI Agents and Agentic AI amplify five classical ethical principles – transparency, justice and fairness, non-maleficence, responsibility and accountability, and privacy – through three structural shifts: broad agency, heightened impact on human autonomy, and deeper human-technology entanglement. Their responsibility-and-accountability analysis is the strand most directly relevant to the present study’s enforcement-audit gap finding. Cranefield and Oren (2026) define accountability for multi-agent systems through a cross-disciplinary literature survey, providing the theoretical foundation for our operationalization of accountability gaps.

A growing body of empirical work measures the MCP ecosystem from complementary angles. Li et al. (2025) characterize attack surface by tallying OS/runtime API invocations across 2,562 servers and call for “automated trust assessment” as future work. Hasan et al. (2025) report CWE-style vulnerability and code-smell patterns across 1,899 stratified servers. Guo et al. (2025) provide ecosystem-health metrics (marketplace inflation, dependency monocultures, maintenance cadence) across 8,401 servers. Two industry research efforts – Astrix Security (2025) and Knostic (2025) – report credential-presence statistics that broadly corroborate this study’s 81% authentication finding. Zheng and Zhang (2026) provide a formal counterpart through TLA+ model-checking of the MCP specification and reference SDKs, demonstrating that the spec mandates audit only at the SHOULD level. Huang et al. (2026) measure caller identity confusion across 6,137 real-world MCP servers, finding that 46.4% exhibit insecure authorization, with one-time, server-level authorization the norm and per-tool authorization rarely enforced. None of these works measures governance posture against an established access-control framework or distinguishes authentication from actor attribution at ecosystem scale; this study supplies the integrated measurement.

At a broader level, Schroeder de Witt et al. (2026) frame multi-agent security as a distinct research discipline anticipating threats that emerge or amplify through agent-to-agent interactions – including the trust-chaining concerns this study explicitly leaves unmeasured (Section 2.3). Their analysis positions individual MCP servers as the substrate on which multi-agent governance composes, a substrate whose governance posture this study is the first to measure at population scale.

2. Background and Related Work

2.1 The Model Context Protocol

The Model Context Protocol (MCP) defines a client-server architecture for AI agent tool interaction. An MCP server registers tools – named operations with typed input schemas and descriptions – that agents can discover and invoke at runtime. The protocol supports multiple transport types (stdio, Server-Sent Events, streamable HTTP) and includes optional tool annotations (readOnlyHint, destructiveHint, idempotentHint, openWorldHint) that declare behavioral properties.

MCP adoption has accelerated since its initial release by Anthropic. The MCP Registry contained

22,391 entries (7,541 unique latest versions) at the time of our analysis, with npm hosting 8,700 packages and PyPI 3,279 packages containing MCP-related keywords. The ecosystem is growing rapidly: Stein (2026) reports a doubling period of approximately 3.6 months. This growth makes ecosystem-scale measurement both urgent and methodologically challenging, as findings describe a rapidly evolving snapshot.

2.2 Agent governance frameworks

Multiple frameworks now prescribe governance controls for agentic systems. The OWASP Top 10 for Agentic Applications (2026) identifies ten risk categories including Agent Goal Hijack, Tool Misuse, and Identity and Privilege Abuse. The OWASP MCP Top 10 (2025) provides protocol-specific risk taxonomy. SAFE-MCP (Linux Foundation/OpenID Foundation) proposes a common security baseline for MCP-enabled systems, adapting MITRE ATT&CK methodology with 85 techniques across 14 tactic categories. The NIST AI Agent Standards Initiative (2026) coordinates federal voluntary guidance through the Center for AI Standards and Innovation, with an open Request for Information explicitly soliciting “measurement methodologies for agent security.”

More recently, the Coalition for Secure AI (CoSAI), a heavyweight industry consortium with contributors from Anthropic, IBM, Google, Meta, Amazon, Intel, and Cisco, has published two complementary frameworks under OASIS Open Project auspices. The Model Context Protocol Security white paper (CoSAI 2025) enumerates twelve threat categories (MCP-T1 through MCP-T12) with eleven prescribed control families. The Agentic Identity and Access Management document (CoSAI 2026) defines nine core principles for agent identity, capability-bound delegation, and the OAuth 2.0 Token Exchange `sub / act.sub` claim structure that operationalizes actor attribution. The UC Berkeley CLTC Agentic AI Risk-Management Standards Profile (Madkour et al. 2026) extends the NIST AI Risk Management Framework with Govern/Map/Measure/Manage subcategories specific to agentic systems, explicitly identifying in its Measure 3.2 the absence of established “measurement techniques” for many AI risks. At the meta-taxonomic level, the MIT AI Risk Repository (Slattery et al. 2026) integrates 1,725 risks from 74 source frameworks across seven domains – including AI system security (2.2) and governance failure (6.5) – providing the broader taxonomic context within which the more specific MCP and agentic-AI frameworks operate.

At the time of writing (mid-2026), one protocol-level development illustrates the direction of travel, and the MCP authorization model is itself in active revision. The MCP project’s Enterprise-Managed Authorization (EMA) lets an enterprise identity provider mediate the client-server authorization handshake, so that organizations can centrally govern which MCP connections are permitted (Model Context Protocol 2026a). EMA addresses enterprise identity and authorization at the first connection hop; it does not specify how principal identity propagates across downstream tool invocations or into per-server audit records – a scope limit we return to in Section 5.5. The authorization specification is advancing in parallel – step-up scope accumulation was clarified in SEP-2350 and folded into the forthcoming 2026-07-28 release candidate (Model Context Protocol 2026b), while a proposal for per-tool authorization scopes (SEP-1880) was considered and closed without adoption – so the EMA snapshot described here is one stage of a moving trajectory, and per-tool authorization scope remains unstandardized.

These frameworks converge on a common set of prescribed controls: identity management, authorization scoping, audit logging, human-in-the-loop confirmation, and least-privilege enforcement. What they lack is empirical evidence of adoption, which Sections 4 and 5 supply.

2.3 ABAC architecture and agent governance

The XACML 3.0 standard (OASIS, 2013) defines four architectural components for attribute-based access control: the Policy Administration Point (PAP), which authors policies; the Policy Information Point (PIP), which supplies attribute context; the Policy Decision Point (PDP), which evaluates requests against policies; and the Policy Enforcement Point (PEP), which enforces decisions at the resource boundary.

Agent systems operating across chained tool boundaries require two additional concerns not fully addressed by XACML. First, trust chaining: when an agent invokes a tool on one MCP server and that server invokes a tool on another, the original principal’s identity and authorization context must propagate across boundaries. Schroeder de Witt et al. (2026, Table 2) characterize the failure mode here as attribution decay – attribution that “degrades with every delegation hop” – and observe that multi-agent compositions “exceed the sum of individually measured components.” XACML’s Context Handler mediates between a single PEP and PDP but does not address multi-hop delegation. Second, post-action audit with actor attribution: XACML defines obligations (actions the PEP must fulfill alongside the access decision, per Section 7.18) but does not specify audit log structure, attribution requirements, or tamper-evidence mechanisms. NIST SP 800-162 addresses both gaps – Section 5.4 for attribute assurance across boundaries, and Section 5.7 for the audit function, which specifies that audit records should capture “the subject, action, resource, and decision for each access request.”

This study operationalizes the enforcement and audit concerns as measurable indicators in MCP server source code:

Concern	XACML	NIST 800-162	Indicators	Coverage
Policy authoring	PAP	S5.1-5.3	MCP annotation adoption, read/write separation	Partial
Attribute context	PIP	S5.4	–	Not measured (runtime)
Policy decision	PDP	S5.5	–	Not measured (runtime)
Trust chaining	Context Handler	S5.4	–	Not measured
Enforcement	PEP	S5.6	authentication, perToolAuth, confirmationGates, stagedExecution, rateLimiting, leastPrivilege	Direct (6 indicators)
Audit	Obligations	S5.7	auditLogging, actorAttribution	Direct (2 indicators)

The six concerns partition into three measurement tiers. Two are directly observable from source: enforcement and audit. One is partially observable: policy authoring, via MCP annotation adoption and read/write separation. The remaining three – attribute context, policy decision, and trust chaining – require runtime instrumentation not available from static source analysis. The paper’s

scope is explicitly limited to the two directly observable concerns, enforcement and audit, with policy authoring reported as a partial proxy. The enforcement row lists six primary indicators; Table 2 additionally reports a seventh, sensitive-read protection – a derived compound indicator, Present only where a server both exposes sensitive-read tools and gates them with authentication – which is excluded from the governance posture scores (Section 4.7).

2.4 Read/write classification and its limits

Prior work classifies MCP tools by capability domain. Stein (2026) uses a perception/reasoning/action taxonomy derived from LLM-based classification. Our classification uses a different axis oriented toward governance: does the tool modify persistent state?

We define the persistent-effect rule: if calling the tool twice produces a different world state than not calling it at all, and the effect survives process termination, the tool is classified as write. This rule was validated through human classification of 100 tools, achieving kappa = 0.940 (almost perfect agreement) between LLM re-evaluation and human judgment. The deterministic keyword heuristic achieved kappa = 0.518 (moderate) against the same human baseline, confirming that LLM-assisted classification substantially improves reliability.

However, read/write classification alone is insufficient for governance assessment. A tool that retrieves patient records, exports API keys, or queries credit scores is correctly classified as “read” under the persistent-effect rule – it does not modify state. But it is governance-relevant: its output would be subject to access control, audit requirements, or regulatory obligations in any well-governed deployment.

2.5 The sensitivity dimension

We introduce a sensitivity axis orthogonal to read/write classification. A tool is classified as sensitive if it meaningfully affects confidentiality, integrity, availability, autonomy, or accountability – regardless of whether it modifies persistent state.

Sensitivity classification uses boundary-aware keyword matching across three signal categories:

- **Data-domain signals** (primarily confidentiality): keywords indicating the tool handles protected data domains – PII, credentials, financial records, medical data, legal/regulatory content.
- **Action-scope signals** (primarily autonomy and integrity): keywords indicating governance-relevant actions – financial transactions, code execution, infrastructure lifecycle operations.
- **Context-dependent signals**: keywords that indicate sensitivity only when combined with qualifying terms. For example, “config” is not sensitive alone (many tools read application configuration), but “config” combined with “secret,” “credential,” or “token” more likely indicates sensitive configuration access.

A single specific keyword match is sufficient for classification, but the matching algorithm enforces word boundaries (underscore, hyphen, dot, space, camelCase transitions) to prevent false positives from substring collisions (e.g., “secret” in “secretary” or “charge” in “formal charge”).

Sensitivity classification was validated through human classification of 100 tools (60 deterministically classified as sensitive, 40 as non-sensitive), achieving kappa = 0.675 (substantial), with precision = 0.817 and recall = 0.907 against the deterministic classifier. The eleven false positives

arise from keyword matches in non-governance contexts – chemistry and literature search, aggregate occupation statistics, and description-level credential mentions – and, most instructively, from negation- and context-blind matches in which the matched term is negated or names an access gate rather than the tool’s data (for example a board described as “no payment required”, a scan run “without secret detection”, a generic key-value store, and listings that return only masked or name-only credential metadata). The five false negatives arise from domain-specific vocabulary not in the keyword list (cryptocurrency wallet signing, database rollback, security probing, file deletion, and customer-profile PII).

3. Method

3.1 Population and sampling frame

The study population comprises 17,563 unique MCP servers enumerated from three canonical registries as of May 4, 2026:

- **MCP Registry** (registry.modelcontextprotocol.io): 22,391 raw entries, 7,541 unique isLatest entries
- **npm**: 8,700 packages matching MCP-server keywords
- **PyPI**: 3,279 packages matching MCP-related names

Candidates were deduplicated by repository URL, producing a population of 13,308 servers with cloneable source code and 4,255 remote-only servers (no source available).

The sample was drawn using stratified random sampling with a seeded pseudorandom number generator (mulberry32, seed 20260512) across six strata defined by package ecosystem and MCP Registry presence:

Stratum	Population	Target	Final
npm + MCP Registry	2,864	190	181
npm only	6,333	220	207
PyPI + MCP Registry	1,089	155	152
PyPI only	1,055	155	139
Other ecosystem	2,095	95	81
Remote only	1,045	185	185
Total	14,481	1,000	945

Two notes reconcile the population column. First, the remote-only stratum draws from 1,045 servers rather than the full 4,255 remote-only population: only remote servers listed in the MCP Registry carry a declared endpoint suitable for RPC introspection (Section 3.4), so the 3,210 remote-only npm and PyPI entries that lack a registry endpoint are unanalyzable by any method and fall outside the sampling frame. Second, the cloneable stratum populations are filter-match counts rather than a disjoint partition: a server published to more than one ecosystem (for example both npm and PyPI) is counted in each matching stratum, so the per-stratum populations sum to slightly more than the 13,308 unique cloneable servers, and the Total row is a column sum over non-disjoint strata. These stratum populations count post-deduplication servers classified by package ecosystem and registry presence – a different layer from the raw per-registry enumeration counts in the list above.

In particular, the npm and PyPI keyword-search totals (8,700 and 3,279) are enumeration inputs, not the npm and PyPI stratum populations: a registry-discovered server that is also npm- or PyPI-published is classified into that ecosystem without appearing in the keyword-search count, so the npm strata (2,864 + 6,333) need not sum to the 8,700 npm-search total. Sampling itself assigns each drawn server to a single stratum in the order listed, so no server is drawn twice.

Of the 1,000-server target, 815 fell in the cloneable strata and 185 in the remote-only stratum. The cloneable draw was supplemented with 184 replacement servers for dead repositories, for 999 cloneable repositories retrieved. Of these 999, 51 had been deleted or renamed since the snapshot and 188 were confirmed non-MCP by LLM verification (proxies, scaffolding tools, client libraries, SDK wrappers); excluding both leaves 760 source-available servers. With the 185 remote-only servers, the final corpus contains 945: 760 source-available and 185 remote-only.

3.2 Deterministic analysis pipeline

Each source-available server is shallow-cloned and analyzed through a deterministic pipeline:

Tool extraction uses language-specific regex patterns for Python (decorator patterns including `@mcp.tool`, `@server.tool`, `add_tool`, class-based Tool inheritance), TypeScript/JavaScript (`.tool()`, `registerTool`, object-style definitions), and Go (`mcp.Tool` struct literals). Contextual refinement reclassifies tools where keyword signals conflict with description context (e.g., “execute” in a read-only SQL context is downgraded from write to read).

Two-axis classification assigns each tool a read/write classification using the persistent-effect keyword heuristic and a sensitivity classification using boundary-aware keyword matching. When MCP tool annotations are present in source (`readOnlyHint`, `destructiveHint`), they override keyword-based read/write classification.

Governance pattern scanning detects source-level signals for authentication (Bearer tokens, OAuth patterns, API key validation), audit logging (logger calls, structured logging), confirmation gates (user confirmation prompts, approval flows), staged execution (dry-run, preview, sandbox patterns), actor attribution (principal identifiers within proximity of log calls), rate limiting, and least privilege scoping (OAuth scopes, permission sets).

Gap detection identifies seven named accountability gap patterns from the combination of tool classifications and governance patterns:

1. **ungated-write**: write tools with no confirmation gate or staged-execution mechanism co-located in their source file
2. **global-auth-over-sensitive-tools**: single authentication layer applied uniformly across tools with materially different sensitivity levels
3. **auth-without-actor-logging**: authentication patterns present alongside logging, but log statements do not carry principal identifiers within proximity
4. **logging-without-attribution**: logging present but no principal identifiers and no authentication
5. **destructive-without-audit-trail**: irreversible operations (drop, delete, truncate, destroy) with no logging in the same file
6. **sensitive-read-without-auth**: tools accessing sensitive data with no authentication mechanism
7. **sensitive-read-without-logging**: sensitive data access with no audit logging in the tool’s source file

Each server is coded for the 11 governance indicators reported in Table 2 (Present/Absent/Indeterminate), spanning enforcement, audit, and policy-authoring concerns. The analysis instrument records additional indicator fields outside this study’s scope – three controls that require human review and are not determinable from static analysis (self-modification prevention, sub-agent authority constraints, and permission-boundary enforcement, oriented toward human-oversight and multi-agent concerns) and a sensitive-capability-isolation design check – which are not analyzed here.

3.3 LLM verification layer

An LLM verification pass using Claude Opus (claude-opus-4-6) via the Claude Code CLI supplements the deterministic analysis. For each source-available server, the verification prompt receives code regions prioritized by MCP relevance (dependency manifests, MCP-importing files, entry points) within a budget of approximately 30,000 tokens. The LLM produces three outputs:

1. **MCP server confirmation:** whether the repository implements an MCP server (yes/no/uncertain with cited evidence)
2. **Supplementary tool extraction:** tools using registration patterns not captured by the deterministic regex extractor
3. **Classification validation:** read/write classification with rationale citing source code

LLM verification covered 664 of 760 source-available servers (87%). The remaining 96 servers produced CLI timeouts on large repositories and were analyzed deterministically only. LLM verification identified 188 non-MCP repositories that were excluded from the final corpus. In an earlier configuration the LLM pass extracted 4,124 tools beyond the deterministic baseline of the time, concentrated in dynamic registration patterns the regex extractor did not yet capture; the deterministic extractor was subsequently extended to recognize those patterns (Section 3.2), raising deterministic coverage to 14,282 tools across 85% of source-available servers. For servers using consistent registration patterns, deterministic extraction proved not merely cheaper but more complete than the LLM pass: in several source-available cases it recovered more tools than the LLM reported (for example 39 vs 19, 25 vs 11, and 107 vs 49), because the LLM’s fixed per-server token budget truncates long tool inventories. This completeness claim concerns tool *enumeration* and should not be conflated with the $\kappa = 0.518$ reported in Section 2.4: that figure measures the reliability of the deterministic keyword heuristic for read/write *classification* of already-extracted tools, a separate task on which the LLM verification layer is the more reliable component. Deterministic extraction is the more complete enumerator; LLM verification is the more reliable classifier. The LLM layer’s role is correspondingly bounded to MCP confirmation, coverage of irregular registration shapes, and classification validation.

3.4 Remote-only analysis

The 185 remote-only servers (no cloneable source code) were analyzed via MCP protocol introspection. The RPC client performs MCP protocol negotiation (initialize, then tools/list) over streamable-HTTP and SSE transports. Of 138 servers with declared endpoints in the MCP Registry, 23 returned tool inventories (151 tools total). All governance indicators for remote-only servers are coded Indeterminate – the absence of source code means enforcement and audit patterns cannot be assessed. The opacity of remote-only servers is itself a finding about ecosystem inspectability.

3.5 Human validation

Two validation exercises were conducted, each on a sample of 100 tools classified by the first author.

Read/write validation: 100 tools stratified across heuristic-LLM disagreements (49) and agreements (51), drawn from the pilot corpus. Decision rule: persistent-effect. Three-way comparison:

Comparison	n	Agreement	Kappa
LLM (Opus) vs Human	100	97%	0.940 (almost perfect)
Heuristic vs Human	75	76%	0.518 (moderate)
Heuristic vs LLM	75	76%	0.520 (moderate)

The heuristic comparisons are computed on 75 of the 100 tools: 25 tools carry no read/write signal under the deterministic heuristic (coded Indeterminate) and are excluded from those rows, while the LLM-versus-human comparison retains all 100. The 49/51 split above is the pilot heuristic-LLM stratification used to draw the sample; under the final re-evaluated labels the heuristic and LLM agree on 57 of the 100 tools (43 disagreements).

Sensitivity validation: 100 tools (60 det-sensitive, 40 det-non-sensitive) drawn from the full corpus. The validation sample is intentionally stratified to oversample sensitive-classified tools because their corpus prevalence (2.6%) is too low for random sampling to yield enough positive cases for precision/recall estimation. Consequently, the precision and recall figures below are computed against this enriched validation sample, not against a random sample of the corpus; the 9.5% prevalence of **sensitive-read-without-logging** reported in Section 4.2 is a separate corpus-level statistic. Decision rule: would the tool’s output or action be subject to access control, audit requirements, or regulatory obligations in a well-governed deployment?

Metric	Value
Agreement	84%
Kappa	0.675 (substantial), 95% CI [0.53, 0.81]
Precision	0.817
Recall	0.907
False positives	11
False negatives	5

The precision and recall figures above are computed against the 60-sensitive / 40-non-sensitive stratified validation sample, not against a random sample at corpus prevalence (2.6% sensitive). In a random sample at corpus prevalence, with a keyword matcher tuned to that vocabulary, precision and recall figures would be lower than reported here; the validation establishes classifier reliability on a deliberately enriched sample, not field precision at corpus base rates.

All primary classifications were performed by a single coder (the first author). To test the reproducibility of these classifications, a second coder independently re-coded both validation samples (the 100-tool read/write sample and the 100-tool sensitivity sample), blind to the first author’s labels and to the automated heuristic, LLM, and deterministic outputs. Inter-coder agreement was kappa = 0.840 (almost perfect) on the read/write sample and kappa = 0.568 (moderate, 95% CI [0.40, 0.71]) on the sensitivity sample (n = 100 each). The read/write classifications are thus

independently reproducible. The lower sensitivity agreement reflects the construct’s subjective upper boundary: the second coder’s disagreements concentrate on borderline cases, not on the clear positives (credentials, payments, authentication) or clear negatives, and the sensitivity findings are reported accordingly as directional.

3.6 Use of large language models in the study

Large language models (Claude Opus, claude-opus-4-6) were used in four roles. All empirical claims derive from the analysis pipeline of Sections 3.2–3.3, and the first author verified every reported number, citation, and framework mapping against the source artifacts (the `cc-mcp-audit` evidence corpus and the derived statistics in `code/` and `data/`).

1. **Production analysis pipeline.** Claude Opus (claude-opus-4-6) via the Claude Code CLI performed the LLM verification pass described in Section 3.3: MCP server confirmation, supplementary tool extraction, and read/write classification with cited rationale. Throughput was rate-limited to one server in flight at a time with a 5-second inter-request delay and three retries on transient failures. Coverage was 664 of 760 source-available servers (87%); the remaining 96 hit CLI timeouts on large repositories and fell back to deterministic-only analysis.
2. **Validation reliability comparisons.** The kappa figures in Section 3.5 compare LLM classification against human-coded ground truth on stratified samples; the LLM output is the subject of validation, not the standard it is measured against.
3. **Manuscript preparation.** Drafts of this manuscript were composed and revised with LLM assistance, limited to structural editing and prose revision.
4. **Framework-mapping synthesis.** The gap-pattern-to-OWASP/CoSAI MCP-T mappings (Section 5.4) and the multi-paper comparison (Section 5.7) were drafted with LLM assistance and checked against the cited source documents.

The reproduction package includes the LLM verification prompts, raw LLM outputs, and the deterministic pipeline source code, enabling independent re-execution of every LLM-assisted step.

4. Results

4.1 Corpus overview

The final corpus contains 945 servers: 760 source-available and 185 remote-only. The deterministic pipeline extracted 14,282 tools from source-available servers (up from 10,335 before the extractor’s pattern coverage was expanded; see Section 3.2). Among source-available servers, 85% yielded at least one extracted tool. Language distribution: TypeScript (48%), Python (40%), JavaScript (7%), Go (2%), unknown (3%).

4.2 Accountability gap prevalence

Gap detection requires source code analysis and is limited to source-available servers (N=760). Remote-only servers have all governance indicators coded Indeterminate and are excluded from gap prevalence calculations.

Among 760 source-available servers, 539 (70.9%) exhibit at least one accountability gap. Table 1 reports prevalence with 95% Wilson score confidence intervals.

Table 1: Gap pattern prevalence among source-available servers (N=760)

Pattern	Count	Prevalence	95% CI
Any gap	539	70.9%	[67.6%, 74.0%]
global-auth-over-sensitive-tools	308	40.5%	[37.1%, 44.1%]
auth-without-actor-logging	303	39.9%	[36.4%, 43.4%]
ungated-write	218	28.7%	[25.6%, 32.0%]
destructive-without-audit-trail	103	13.6%	[11.3%, 16.2%]
sensitive-read-without-logging	72	9.5%	[7.6%, 11.8%]
logging-without-attribution	43	5.7%	[4.2%, 7.5%]
sensitive-read-without-auth	5	0.7%	[0.3%, 1.5%]

The two most prevalent gaps are near-equal: global authentication applied uniformly across tools of differing sensitivity (41%) and authenticated access without actor-attributed logging (40%). The latter is the central structural finding of this study: these servers gate access through authentication but cannot attribute post-authentication actions to specific principals in their audit trails.

4.3 Governance indicator prevalence

Table 2: Indicator prevalence among source-available servers (N=760)

Indicator	Present	%	ABAC Concern
Authentication	616	81%	Enforcement (PEP)
Audit logging	475	62%	Audit (S5.7)
Staged execution	460	61%	Enforcement (PEP)
Read/write separation	631	83%	Policy authoring (PAP)
Confirmation gates	328	43%	Enforcement (PEP)
Rate limiting	247	32%	Enforcement (PEP)
Least privilege	163	21%	Enforcement (PEP)
Actor attribution	129	17%	Audit (S5.7)
Sensitive-read protection [†]	86	11%	Enforcement (PEP)
Per-tool auth	36	5%	Enforcement (PEP)
MCP annotation adoption	28	4%	Policy authoring (PAP)

[†] *Sensitive-read protection* is a subgroup indicator: it is coded Indeterminate for the 669 servers with no sensitive-read tools. The $86/760 = 11\%$ figure expresses the compound rate (server exposes sensitive reads AND gates them with authentication) and is shown here for table-format comparability. The subgroup rate among the 91 servers with sensitive-read tools is $86/91 = 95\%$ Present (the 5 Absent servers correspond to the `sensitive-read-without-auth` gap pattern in Table 1).

The enforcement-audit gap is visible in the contrast between authentication (81%) and actor attribution (17%). Most servers gate access. Few can trace actions to actors.

A sensitivity analysis bounds the authentication-inflation concern flagged in Section 6, item 3. Under a stricter detection regime requiring at least one auth signal in server-implementation code –

excluding test files, vendored dependencies, examples, and documentation – authentication adoption is 79.2% (95% CI [76.2%, 81.9%]), and the enforcement-audit gap shifts from 64.1 to 62.2 percentage points. Of 616 lenient-regime auth-present servers, 602 (97.7%) retain Present status under strict detection; the remaining 14 servers have auth signals only in non-server-code locations and account for the 1.9-percentage-point inflation. Across all auth signals aggregated over auth-present servers ($n = 126,378$ matches), 70.0% originate in server code, 27.2% in test files, 1.5% in documentation, 1.2% in examples or mocks, and 0.1% in vendored dependencies. The structural finding survives the alternative regime.

4.4 Subgroup analysis by stratum

Table 3: Per-stratum governance posture (source-available only)

Stratum	N	Tools/server	Gap rate	Auth	Logging	Gates	Score (Model A)
npm + registry	181	17.9	76%	83%	64%	48%	4.81
npm only	207	28.9	77%	86%	68%	50%	5.15
pypi + registry	152	16.2	74%	84%	61%	47%	4.74
pypi only	139	14.1	65%	73%	63%	35%	3.65
other ecosystem	81	5.9	49%	72%	49%	22%	3.23

Contrary to the intuition that listing in the curated MCP Registry signals governance maturity, registry presence shows no significant association with gap prevalence (70% vs 72%, chi-squared = 0.3, $p = 0.56$, OR = 0.91): registry-listed servers – which include the registry-sourced “other ecosystem” stratum – are no more or less likely to exhibit gaps than servers absent from the registry. Language (TypeScript vs Python) likewise shows no significant association (74% vs 69%, $p = 0.16$).

4.5 Sensitivity dimension findings

Of 14,282 heuristic-extracted tools, 375 (2.6%) are classified as sensitive: 211 in the confidentiality category (credentials, PII, financial data), 158 in the autonomy category (financial transactions, external communications), and 6 in the integrity category (code execution). Of these, 198 are classified as sensitive-read: tools that expose protected data without modifying state.

Ninety-one source-available servers contain at least one sensitive-read tool. Of these, 72 (79%) exhibit the sensitive-read-without-logging gap – sensitive data access with no co-located audit trail. This is an audit gap, not an access gap: only 5 of the 91 servers expose sensitive reads with no authentication at all (the **sensitive-read-without-auth** pattern, Table 1), so 95% gate the data behind authentication – it is reached by authenticated callers, but the access goes unrecorded.

To bound the contribution of keyword false positives to these counts, we apply a downgrade-only alternative regime, analogous to the strict authentication-detection regime of Section 4.3. The regime re-derives sensitivity after demoting any tool whose matched signal sits entirely in a non-governance context: a negated term (“Free, no payment required”), an access-gate price rather than

the tool’s own action (“Requires Founder sub or kit purchase”), a values-masked read (“returns names only, not values”), or a generic key-value store (“persistent key-value store ... e.g. a budget config”). Because the regime only removes flags, every recomputed count is a conservative lower bound. It demotes 22 of 375 sensitive flags (5.9%), leaving 353 sensitive and 180 sensitive-read tools across 82 source-available servers. Critically, the sensitive-read-without-logging proportion does not fall: 67 of 82 servers (82%), versus 72 of 91 (79%) under the primary classifier, because the demoted false positives were concentrated on better-instrumented servers. The blind-spot finding is therefore not an artifact of keyword over-matching. The regime is reported as a sensitivity analysis, not a retuning of the primary classifier; the keyword lists themselves were not modified (Section 6, item 1).

4.6 Association analysis

Table 4: Factors associated with gap presence (chi-squared, N=760)

Factor	Gap rate	chi-squared	p	OR
Tool count > 10 vs 1-10	94% vs 63%	83.4	< 0.001	9.35
Has extracted tools vs zero	76% vs 42%	55.4	< 0.001	4.46
Has sensitive tools	98% vs 66%	50.5	< 0.001	20.81
Has authentication	76% vs 49%	42.9	< 0.001	3.37
Registry presence	70% vs 72%	0.3	0.56	0.91
TypeScript vs Python	74% vs 69%	1.9	0.16	1.27

Tool count is the strongest predictor: servers with more than 10 tools have over nine times the odds of exhibiting gaps (OR = 9.35). Sensitive-tool presence is even more strongly associated (OR = 20.81), though the modest sample size (123 servers with any sensitive tool) warrants caution. This 123-server count is the any-sensitive set used for the Table 4 association; it is broader than the 91 source-available servers with sensitive-*read* tools reported in Section 4.5, which is the relevant denominator for the sensitive-read governance gap.

The positive association between authentication and gap presence (OR = 3.37) is structural, not paradoxical: authentication is a precondition for one of the two most prevalent gaps (auth-without-actor-logging). A server with no authentication cannot exhibit an authentication-logging disconnect.

The “has extracted tools vs zero” association (OR = 4.46) speaks to the indicator-measurement consequences of extraction coverage. Servers from which the pipeline extracted no tools are not a random subsample of the corpus. These tend to use dynamic registration patterns or to be thin wrappers around upstream SDKs, and exhibit gap rates 34 percentage points lower than servers with extracted tools (42% vs 76%). This means apparent ecosystem governance posture is partly an artifact of which servers expose enough surface to be measured, and the extraction-coverage limitation (Section 6) has a directional effect on the reported gap prevalence: a more complete extractor would likely raise the gap rate, not lower it.

4.7 Governance posture scoring

We compute governance posture scores using two complementary models:

Model A (simple additive): each indicator scored Present = 1, Absent = 0, Indeterminate excluded from denominator. Score scaled 0-10. For the 760 source-available servers: mean = 4.51, SD = 2.97, median = 4.29, IQR = [2.50, 7.14]. The distribution is roughly uniform with 34% scoring Low (0-2.5), 27% Mid (2.5-5.0), and 39% High (5.0-10.0).

Model B (concern subscores): enforcement indicators (6, weighted 1x each) and audit indicators (2, weighted 2x each) computed separately, then combined. The 2x weight on audit indicators reflects the finding that the audit concern is the weaker of the two measured concerns.

Concern	Mean	SD	Median
Enforcement	4.42	2.97	4.00
Audit	5.22	4.45	5.00

Audit’s higher subscore mean (5.22 versus 4.42 for enforcement) does not indicate uniformly stronger audit posture; it reflects bimodal scoring. The audit score distribution is sharply bimodal: 38% of servers score 0 (no logging or attribution) and 42% score 10. That top bucket tracks logging, not attribution, however: of the 318 servers scoring 10, only 129 record both logging and actor attribution, while the other 189 log without a detectable attribution signal (their attribution is coded Indeterminate and excluded from the subscore denominator). The audit score is therefore essentially all-or-nothing on logging. The underlying weakness is concentrated in actor attribution, present in only 17% of servers (Table 2), which the 2x audit weighting only partially exposes because the relatively high logging-adoption rate (62%) carries the combined subscore upward.

Figure 1: Enforcement vs Audit scores (N=760)

	Audit Low	Audit Mid	Audit High
Enforcement High	17 (2%)	21 (3%)	168 (22%)
Enforcement Mid	107 (14%)	84 (11%)	124 (16%)
Enforcement Low	161 (21%)	52 (7%)	26 (3%)

The distribution clusters in three cells: Low/Low (161 servers, no governance), High/High (168, well-governed), and Mid-Enforcement/Low-Audit (107, enforcement without accountability). The 107-server cell is the structural governance failure this paper identifies: servers that gate access but cannot attribute actions. Including the 17 servers with High enforcement and Low audit, a total of 124 servers (16%) have functioning enforcement with no functioning audit.

Servers with gaps score higher than those without (mean 5.26 vs 2.68) because gaps require governance infrastructure to exist. A server with zero governance has zero gaps and zero score.

4.8 Ecosystem inspectability

Twenty percent of the sample (185 remote-only servers) cannot be assessed from any governance surface. Of 138 with declared endpoints, only 23 (17%) returned tool inventories via RPC introspection. The remainder are placeholder registrations, authentication-gated, or staging templates.

Among source-available servers, 15% have no extractable tools despite importing MCP frameworks (down from 37% as the deterministic extractor’s pattern coverage expanded; Section 3.2), indicating registration patterns not captured by automated extraction. The residual is characterized

by a documented structural taxonomy – bespoke registration frameworks, runtime/dynamic tool construction, and cross-language packaging – rather than left unexplained. The extraction gap is a real characteristic of the ecosystem: diverse and dynamic tool registration patterns limit the reach of any static analysis approach.

5. Discussion

5.1 Governance posture mapped to ABAC architecture

The six ABAC concerns provide a diagnostic frame for the empirical findings:

Enforcement (PEP): 81% of source-available servers implement some form of authentication, but only 5% implement per-tool authorization. 43% have confirmation gates. Enforcement exists but is coarse-grained – most servers apply a single authentication gate to all tools regardless of sensitivity. A user authorized to list files has the same access as one authorized to delete databases.

Audit (NIST 800-162 S5.7): 62% have logging, but only 17% have actor-attributed logging. Actor attribution, not audit as a whole, is the specific deficit: it is among the lowest-prevalence indicators measured (Table 2), and Section 4.7 shows that the audit subscore’s higher mean is an artifact of bimodal logging adoption rather than stronger attribution. The enforcement-audit cross-tabulation (Figure 1) identifies 124 servers (16%) with functioning enforcement but no functioning audit – the structural governance failure at the center of this study.

Policy authoring (PAP): MCP tool annotation adoption (28 of 760 source-available servers, 3.7%; Table 2) is the only source-visible proxy for policy-authoring intent, alongside read/write separation. The protocol provides governance metadata primitives (`readOnlyHint`, `destructiveHint`, `idempotentHint`, `openWorldHint`), but ecosystem adoption is both sparse and concentrated: the 592 annotated tools cluster within those 28 servers (roughly 21 each), so annotation is effectively an all-or-nothing engineering decision made by a small minority rather than an incrementally adopted practice. At this prevalence, annotations cannot serve as a reliable ecosystem-wide accountability substrate.

Trust chaining: Not measured from source. Authentication token presence provides no assurance of downstream propagation – a server may validate a Bearer token at its own boundary without forwarding caller identity to tools or downstream servers it invokes. The 40% auth-without-actor-logging rate is partly a symptom of broken trust chains: if identity does not propagate past the first enforcement boundary, downstream components cannot attribute actions.

Decision and attribute context: Not observable from static source analysis. These concerns require runtime instrumentation or proxy interposition that is beyond the scope of this study.

5.2 The auth-without-actor-logging gap

At 40% of source-available servers – statistically tied with global authentication over sensitive tools as the most prevalent gap – this pattern reveals a structural problem: servers invest in authentication but not in connecting that authentication to audit trails. The server verifies that the caller is authorized, executes the requested action, and either does not log the action at all or logs it without recording which authenticated principal initiated it.

The CoSAI Agentic Identity and Access Management framework (CoSAI 2026) gives this connection

its canonical industry vocabulary: tokens issued under the OAuth 2.0 Token Exchange profile (RFC 8693) carry a `sub` claim identifying the subject/principal on whose behalf the action is performed and an `act.sub` claim identifying the agent/actor that actually performed it. The 40% gap we measure is the deployed absence of this `act.sub` propagation into audit logs – the structural primitive the CoSAI framework prescribes is not in the recorded evidence of what happened.

This pattern means governance can verify that access was authorized but cannot determine who took which action after authorization. In incident response, this creates a fundamental attribution problem: if an agent with valid credentials performs an unauthorized action (through prompt injection, scope escalation, or delegation chain compromise), the audit trail cannot distinguish the legitimate agent’s actions from the compromised ones.

The finding is the structural collapse argued in Section 1 made measurable. When the requester, reasoner, actor, and record-keeper merge into a single operational chain, the link most readily severed in practice is the one connecting actor to record. Conventional web-system audit logging tolerates this severance because the human-driven request preserves the principal in session state, browser identity, or transport-layer telemetry that downstream auditing can recover. The agent setting does not preserve those out-of-band identity surfaces: the only authoritative record of which principal authorized the agent’s action is the one the enforcement point chooses to write. Forty percent of source-available servers do not write it. The dominant gap pattern is therefore not a logging deficiency in the conventional sense. Rather, it is a case of the conventional sense becoming inadequate.

5.3 Sensitive reads as a governance blind spot

198 tools across 91 source-available servers expose governance-relevant data as read operations: credential stores, patient records, financial data, API keys. These tools are correctly classified as “read” under the persistent-effect rule – they do not modify state. But they require the same governance infrastructure as write operations: authentication to prevent unauthorized access, logging to create an audit trail, and attribution to trace who accessed what.

The CoSAI Agentic Identity and Access Management framework (CoSAI 2026) formalizes this category in its capability-risk matrix: a “low capability, high risk” quadrant covering “read-only access to sensitive data,” requiring “environment attestation; just-in-time, task-scoped credentials; strict data and tenant scoping.” Our contribution is the empirical measurement of how widely it is unprotected in deployed servers within this category.

Among servers with sensitive-read tools, 79% lack co-located audit logging (81.7% under the downgrade-only negation/context-aware regime that strips keyword false positives; Section 4.5). This means sensitive data can be accessed without record. Governance frameworks that key exclusively on write operations – which is the default in most access control models – leave this exposure entirely unaddressed.

5.4 Mapping to OWASP risk categories

The gap patterns identified in this study provide ecosystem-scale empirical grounding for risk categories defined by the OWASP Top 10 for Agentic Applications (2026), the OWASP MCP Top 10 (2025), and the CoSAI MCP Security threat taxonomy (CoSAI 2025):

Gap pattern	Prevalence	OWASP Agentic	OWASP MCP	CoSAI MCP-T
global-auth-over-sensitive-tools	41%	#7 Identity and Privilege Abuse / #4 Unrestricted Tool Permissions	#2 Excessive Permission Scope	T2
auth-without-actor-logging	40%	#9 Insufficient Logging and Monitoring	#7 Logging and Monitoring Failures	T12
ungated-write	29%	#4 Unrestricted Tool Permissions	#6 Consent and Control Gaps	T2 + T9
destructive-without-audit-trail	14%	#4 Unrestricted Tool Permissions	#8 Missing Lifecycle Controls	T12 + T2
sensitive-read-without-logging	10%	#9 Insufficient Logging and Monitoring	#7 Logging and Monitoring Failures	T5 + T12

These alignments are illustrative rather than exhaustive: each gap pattern may map to more than one framework category, and each category to more than one gap pattern. The naming and scoping of these gap patterns substantially overlap with the OWASP MCP Top 10 and CoSAI MCP-T categories shown above. Importantly, our gap patterns are conjunctive intersections rather than new threat categories: each pattern is defined by the presence of one enforcement primitive (authentication, write capability, sensitivity) alongside the absence of a paired audit or control primitive. For example, *auth-without-actor-logging* operationalizes CoSAI MCP-T12 (Insufficient Logging, Monitoring, and Auditability) specifically: authentication (the control prescribed against threat MCP-T1) is present by construction in this pattern, so the deficit it measures is the absence of attributable logging, not an authentication failure. The pattern isolates the residual T12 gap that persists even where T1 controls have been adopted. We find that existing threat taxonomies are likely sufficient. Our contribution is therefore the empirical measurement of how prevalent these named risks actually are at deployment. The prevalence rates suggest that the risks these frameworks identify are not hypothetical; they describe the ecosystem’s default state.

5.5 Implementation evidence for active federal standards work

The accountability gaps identified in this study correspond directly to the four focus areas of the NIST National Cybersecurity Center of Excellence (NCCoE) concept paper *Accelerating the Adoption of Software and AI Agent Identity and Authorization* (NIST 2026), which is convening voluntary guidance in support of the NIST AI Agent Standards Initiative (NIST AIASI 2026). The initiative’s open Request for Information explicitly solicits “current threat landscape, existing mitigations and their gaps, measurement methodologies for agent security, and best practices for secure development.” This study supplies one such measurement methodology and the corresponding ecosystem-scale baseline.

The concept paper’s four focus areas, the indicators this study observes for each, and the imple-

mentation standards that already exist, are summarized below. The contrast between the second and third columns is the finding: the standards are present everywhere; their deployed adoption is not.

Focus area	Measured adoption (this study)	Existing implementation standards
Identification	authentication 81%, actor attribution 17% (a 64-point gap)	agent-identity drafts – transaction tokens (Raut 2026), Agent Identity Protocol (Prakash 2026)
Authorization	per-tool auth 5%, least privilege 21%, confirmation gates 43%, staged execution 61%	OAuth 2.0/2.1 dynamic scopes; per-tool scopes (SEP-1880, not adopted)
Access delegation (multi-hop; not source-observable)	read indirectly through the 64-point gap	OAuth Token Exchange (RFC 8693), JWT <code>act/sub</code> (RFC 7519), SPIFFE; token-attenuation, actor-chain, and cross-domain drafts (Aimable 2026; Prasad et al. 2026; IETF OAuth Working Group 2026)
Auditing and transparency	audit logging 62%, actor attribution 17% (bimodal: 38% none, 42% full)	OpenTelemetry trace context, RFC 4998 evidence records, hash-chained logs

Two of the four focus areas are directly source-observable. Identification appears as the 64-percentage-point gap between authentication and actor attribution: the mechanisms reach servers, but identity does not propagate into recorded actions. Authorization appears as the 5% per-tool rate – most servers apply a single authorization layer across operations of materially different sensitivity (the global-auth-over-sensitive-tools pattern, 41%). The other two are not observable from a single server. Access delegation is inherently multi-hop, so we read it only indirectly: if `act.sub` propagation is absent in single-hop logs, it is unlikely to appear across hops. Auditing is sharply bimodal, and what is missing is not the standard – RFC 4998 evidence records over OpenTelemetry traces have been available since 2007 – but its adoption.

The shape is the same in every row, and points to standards composition rather than novel protocol design (Fending 2026): the primitives are mature or actively standardizing, and CoSAI prescribes their composition into multi-hop chains with depth limits and revocation cascades (CoSAI 2026). What has not been published is evidence that this composition is adopted, or effective, in deployment. The 124 servers (16%) with functioning enforcement but no functioning audit are the most direct empirical signal of where it is missing in practice – and the evidence input the AIASI program is currently soliciting.

Several mid-2026 developments begin to instantiate parts of this composition, and their scope is instructive. At the protocol layer, the IETF agent-delegation drafts above and a GNAP-for-agents effort (TwigBush 2026) standardize multi-hop token delegation and attenuation. At the orchestration layer, three moves are illustrative. Enterprise-Managed Authorization (EMA) wires an enterprise identity provider into the MCP authorization handshake (Model Context Protocol 2026a), closing part of the identification and authorization focus areas at the first hop; it governs which authenticated connections are permitted but does not require individual servers to attribute logged actions to the calling principal. Emerging vendor agent-identity models give an agent its own per-workspace service account, so that its actions surface in connected systems’ native audit logs under the agent’s identity (Anthropic 2026); these advance identification and audit, but attribute

actions to a single service account rather than to the specific human principal on whose behalf the agent acts – the `sub / act.sub` distinction (Section 5.2) is collapsed, not resolved. And Google’s Agent Gateway, the networking and policy-enforcement component of its Gemini Enterprise Agent Platform, governs agent-to-agent and agent-to-tool connectivity across MCP and A2A traffic at the network boundary (Google Cloud 2026); like EMA it is a connection-boundary policy-enforcement point that advances enforcement but does not propagate the calling principal’s identity into per-server audit records. EMA and these vendor agent-identity models are, at the time of writing, unproven – no efficacy or adoption evidence has been published – and operate at the first hop; the multi-hop delegation protocols are themselves under active standardization (the IETF drafts and GNAP-for-agents above), but none of this work yet carries published deployment-adoption evidence either. None of these closes the server-side actor-attribution gap this study measures: the 64-point enforcement-audit gap persists beneath them, because the audit primitive they presuppose remains the unadopted component, and the 760 servers measured here still write the records.

5.6 Implications for governance framework design

Governance frameworks should not assume that write operations are the only governance-relevant category. The sensitivity dimension is orthogonal to read/write classification and independently important. A read-only tool that retrieves patient records or exports API keys requires the same accountability infrastructure – authentication, logging, attribution – as a tool that modifies data.

The governance posture scoring reveals that the ecosystem distributes roughly into thirds: 34% Low, 27% Mid, 39% High. The audit subscore is sharply bimodal (38% zero, 42% full), suggesting that audit infrastructure is either fully invested in or entirely absent – there is little incremental adoption. This pattern is consistent with audit logging being an architectural decision made early in development rather than a feature added incrementally.

5.7 Comparison with prior MCP measurement work

The MCP ecosystem has attracted a growing set of measurement studies, each measuring a different facet of the same population.

Capability inventory. Stein (2026) classifies 177,000 MCP tools by capability domain (perception, reasoning, action) using LLM-based classification with 14 human validators. Our study classifies 14,282 tools by governance posture (read/write \times sensitivity) plus 11 governance indicators per server, using deterministic-first classification with LLM verification and single-coder validation. The studies are complementary: Stein maps what agents can do; we map what governance infrastructure exists around what agents do. Stein reports that the share of “action” tools (file I/O, code execution, API calls) rose from 27% to 65% of total usage over the 16-month period sampled. Our measurement of the governance surface is essentially static against that growth: 29% of source-available servers have ungated writes, 81% authenticate but only 17% attribute logged actions to principals, and 79% of servers with sensitive-read tools lack co-located audit logging. The two findings read together describe an ecosystem whose capability surface is expanding rapidly while its governance surface, measured here at a single snapshot, sits far behind in level: the prescriptive frameworks of Section 2.2 are plentiful, but the implementation evidence to satisfy them is largely absent.

Attack surface. Li et al. (2025) measure OS/runtime API invocation across 2,562 servers from the `mcpmarket.com` catalog, reporting that 1,438 servers reach Network APIs, 1,237 reach System APIs, 613 reach File APIs, and 25 reach Memory APIs. They identify privilege management as an unaddressed concern and call for “automated trust assessment” as future work. Our governance-posture

measurement supplies that assessment: their attack-surface inventory describes what plugins can reach; our enforcement and audit measurements describe whether those reaches are controlled.

Caller identity and authorization. Huang et al. (2026) measure caller identity confusion across 6,137 real-world MCP servers, finding that 46.4% (2,846 servers) exhibit insecure authorization: a single authorization decision implicitly grants access to multiple, potentially untrusted callers because most servers rely on persistent, server-level authorization states that permit tool invocations after an initial authorization without re-authentication, and few enforce authorization at the per-tool level (their AuthNone and AuthRuntime categories). Their target is the attack vector and its mechanism; ours is the broader governance posture in which it sits. The two converge: their 46.4% caller-blind-authorization finding and our complementary measurements – per-tool authorization present in only 5% of servers and global authentication over sensitive tools the single most prevalent gap (41%) – describe the same coarse, identity-agnostic authorization layer from two methodologies and different sampling frames. The constructs and denominators differ, but the conclusion is mutually reinforcing.

Code quality. Hasan et al. (2025) report eight vulnerability patterns and ten code smells across 1,899 servers stratified across official (88), community-maintained (255), and GitHub-mined (1,556) sources, with reported kappa = 1.0 for vulnerabilities and 0.9 for code smells. Their headline findings include 7.2% general vulnerability rate, 5.5% MCP-specific tool poisoning, and 3.6% credential exposure as a code smell. Their measurement target is code quality and CWE-style vulnerability flags; ours is access-control posture. Hardcoded secrets (their concern) and authentication of callers (ours) are different layers; the two studies are non-overlapping.

Ecosystem health. Guo et al. (2025) measure marketplace inflation, dependency monocultures, and maintenance cadence across 8,401 valid MCP projects (50.9% of raw entries excluded as noise), reporting that 11.2% of servers contain code that potentially invokes sensitive APIs and 21.9% have been inactive for over a year. Their measurement target is ecosystem supply-chain health; ours is governance posture. Both are necessary; neither subsumes the other.

Formal protocol verification. Zheng and Zhang (2026) provide AgentRFC, a TLA+ model-checking verification of MCP and three other agent protocols against an 11-principle Agent Architecture Security Model. They find that the MCP specification mandates audit only at the SHOULD level (their Principle 6 Audit Completeness) and that the reference SDK “performs zero sanitization” for prompt-injection-related checks. Their work is the formal-specification-level counterpart to our deployment-level measurement: they prove the spec permits gaps; we measure how widely those gaps materialize. The convergence is strong – their P6 spec-level audit gap is the same governance failure we measure at 81%/17% across 760 deployed servers.

Industry research. Two industry research efforts (Astrix Security 2025; Knostic 2025) report credential-related statistics that broadly corroborate the present study’s authentication finding. Astrix reports that 88% of 5,200+ servers require credentials, 53% rely on static API keys, 8.5% use OAuth, and 79% pass API keys via environment variables; Knostic, from 1,862 discovered internet-exposed servers, manually verified 119 and found that all 119 responded to unauthenticated tools/list requests. The directional convergence with our 81% authentication adoption finding strengthens external validity, while the methodological differences (vendor research, convenience samples, no validation kappa) leave the academic measurement gap open for the present study to fill.

Multi-agent security agenda. Schroeder de Witt et al. (2026) propose multi-agent security (MASEC) as a distinct research discipline addressing threats that emerge or amplify through agent-

to-agent interactions, explicitly distinguishing their scope from per-server / single-agent surveys. Their position paper synthesizes a ten-category threat taxonomy (privacy, collusion, exploitation, swarm attacks, oversight attacks, cascade attacks, social dilemmas, and others) and an attack-dimension framework (detectability, locality, cascading, multi-step composition, attributability, directness, reversibility). Their work and ours are complementary at different layers: they anticipate threats that emerge from agent interactions; we measure the substrate of individual servers on which those interactions compose. Their observation that “attribution degrades with every delegation hop” (Table 2) and that multi-agent compositions “exceed the sum of individually measured components” are precise statements of what our single-server measurements cannot reach. The 64-percentage-point enforcement-audit gap we measure at the substrate layer is the lower bound on attribution loss that multi-agent delegation only amplifies.

Together these studies form a measurement landscape: capability (Stein), attack surface (Li et al.), governance posture (this study), code quality (Hasan et al.), and ecosystem health (Guo et al.), with formal verification (Zheng and Zhang), caller-identity confusion (Huang et al.), multi-agent security agenda (Schroeder de Witt et al.), and industry corroboration (Astrix, Knostic) as supporting evidence. None alone answers what the others do; the combination provides a comprehensive empirical view of the MCP ecosystem’s security and governance state.

6. Limitations

1. **Classification precision:** Sensitivity classification achieves $\kappa = 0.675$ (precision 0.817, recall 0.907) against human labels, with documented false-positive patterns – keyword matches in non-governance contexts and, notably, negation- and context-blind matches in which the matched term is negated or names an access gate rather than the tool’s data – and false-negative patterns (domain-specific vocabulary not in keyword lists). The keyword lists were not tuned post-validation to preserve methodological transparency.
2. **Extraction coverage:** 15% of source-available servers imported an MCP framework but yielded no tools through automated extraction (down from 37% as the deterministic extractor’s pattern coverage expanded), indicating registration patterns not captured by regex. The residual is characterized by a documented structural taxonomy (bespoke registration frameworks, runtime/dynamic tool construction, cross-language packaging); blind spots remain for the most dynamic cases (tools generated at runtime from configuration or API schemas).
3. **Auth detection inflation (bounded by sensitivity analysis):** The governance pattern scanner detects any authentication-related signal in the codebase. For servers where no tools were extracted, authentication signals may originate from the MCP SDK’s own infrastructure rather than from server-implemented authorization. A sensitivity analysis (reported in Section 4.3) recomputes the indicator under a stricter detection regime requiring at least one auth signal in server-implementation code, excluding test files, vendored dependencies, examples, and documentation. The strict regime yields 79.2% adoption versus 81.1% lenient – a 1.9-percentage-point inflation that does not change the structural finding (gap shifts 64.1 \rightarrow 62.2 pp). Only 14 of 616 auth-present servers (2.3%) have auth signals exclusively in non-server-code locations.
4. **Coder independence:** Primary human classifications were performed by the first author. To provide an independent anchor, a second coder re-coded both validation samples blind

to the first author’s labels and to the automated outputs, with inter-coder agreement of $\kappa = 0.840$ (almost perfect) for read/write and $\kappa = 0.568$ (moderate) for sensitivity (Section 3.5). Inter-method reliability (heuristic vs LLM vs human) is also reported. The read/write classifications are thus independently reproducible; sensitivity agreement is moderate, consistent with the construct’s subjective boundary, and the sensitivity findings carry that reliability caveat accordingly. The classifications rest on two independent coders rather than a single coder, though not on a larger multi-rater panel.

5. **Temporal validity:** The population frame is a point-in-time snapshot (May 4, 2026). The MCP ecosystem is growing rapidly. Findings describe the ecosystem as of the snapshot date and should not be extrapolated without re-enumeration.
6. **Unmeasured ABAC concerns:** Three of six governance concerns (policy decision, attribute context, trust chaining) require runtime instrumentation not available from static source analysis. The study measures enforcement and audit directly and policy authoring as a partial proxy.
7. **Opacity:** 20% of the corpus (185 remote-only servers) is fully opaque, with all indicators coded Indeterminate. These servers contribute to corpus-level statistics but cannot exhibit or be cleared of accountability gaps.

6.1 Direction of bias

The seven limitations above are not symmetric in their effect on the reported gap prevalence. Taken individually:

- *Extraction coverage* (item 2): incomplete extraction means some real governance signals are missed, but the surviving signals are scanned the same way for everyone, so the apparent indicator coverage is a floor rather than a ceiling. The associated direction is conservative – a more complete extractor raises indicator counts unevenly and raises the gap rate, as shown by the $OR = 4.46$ association in Section 4.6 and borne out directly here: expanding the extractor’s pattern coverage lifted the measured any-gap rate from 64% to 71%.
- *Auth detection inflation* (item 3): tested empirically by the strict-regime sensitivity analysis in Section 4.3. The inflation magnitude is bounded at 1.9 percentage points (81.1% lenient vs 79.2% strict); the structural finding survives. This converts a directional concern into a quantified result.
- *Sensitivity classification precision* (item 1): false positives in the keyword matcher inflate the sensitive-tool count, which means the sensitive-read-without-logging prevalence is an upper bound – at the validated precision of 0.817 on the enriched sample, roughly one in six deterministic sensitive flags is a false positive, several of them negation- or context-blind keyword matches. The downgrade-only alternative regime of Section 4.5 quantifies this directly rather than leaving it asserted: stripping the negation- and context-blind matches demotes 22 of 375 sensitive flags yet leaves the sensitive-read-without-logging proportion essentially unchanged (82% versus 79%), so the upper-bound concern is now a bounded one and the structural argument – that sensitive reads are a governance blind spot – survives the correction. False negatives push in the opposite direction and we have less ability to bound them, but the validated κ of 0.675 limits the magnitude.
- *Coder independence* (item 4): inter-method reliability between heuristic, LLM, and human is reported ($\kappa = 0.518$ and 0.940 for read/write, 0.675 for sensitivity), and an independent second coder’s blind recoding agrees at $\kappa = 0.840$ (read/write) and 0.568 (sensitivity)

(Section 3.5). The bias direction from coder composition is uncharacterized but observable, and the released validation samples allow further independent recoding.

- *Temporal validity* (item 5): the snapshot date precedes a doubling period of approximately 3.6 months (Stein, 2026). If the ecosystem’s governance posture is improving over time, the snapshot understates current posture; if it is stable or worsening, the snapshot is representative. Direction unknown but bounded.
- *Unmeasured ABAC concerns* (item 6): the three un-measured concerns are not measured because they require runtime instrumentation. The omission narrows the paper’s scope rather than biasing its reported figures.
- *Opacity* (item 7): the 185 remote-only servers are excluded from gap calculations. If their internal posture mirrored the source-available distribution, the 71% gap rate would carry forward; if remote-only servers are systematically better- or worse-governed, the corpus-level posture would shift accordingly. The opacity itself is the finding for that subset.

One bias runs the other way. Actor attribution is detected as principal identifiers in proximity to log calls (Section 3.2), so a server that binds the principal once in middleware or request-context and logs centrally can attribute actions without leaving a source-co-located signal – it is counted as absent, which inflates the auth-without-actor-logging gap and deflates the 17% attribution figure. It is the one bias here that overstates the gap rather than understating it, and the governance pattern scan, unlike the read/write and sensitivity classifiers, is not separately validated against human coding. Its effect is bounded, however: attribution is Indeterminate for 189 of the 760 servers, every one of which logs, so even treating all of them as actually attributing – the most generous correction the data admit – raises attribution only to 42% and still leaves a 39-percentage-point enforcement-audit gap (attribution cannot exceed the 62% of servers that log at all). The structural finding survives the detector’s worst case. The remaining biases – a fuller extractor, tighter sensitivity classification, longer time horizon, and access to remote-only source – point toward conservatism, so the 70.9% (95% CI: [67.6%, 74.0%]) gap rate is best read as a lower-bound estimate of ecosystem-scale accountability gaps.

7. Conclusion

Agent governance is not merely a policy problem or an identity problem. It is fundamentally an implementation-evidence problem, because governance becomes meaningful only when enforcement constrains behavior and audit proves what happened.

MCP servers provide a measurable empirical surface for this claim. Among 760 source-available servers drawn from the full MCP ecosystem, more than seven in ten exhibit accountability gaps that would prevent governance frameworks from functioning as designed – and because a gap can only be measured where governance infrastructure already exists, that figure is a conservative lower bound. An additional 185 remote-only servers are fully opaque to governance assessment. The most common failure mode is not an absence of security, but the appearance of security without accountability. Servers authenticate users but do not attribute actions, and in doing so log events but do not record who caused them.

The sensitivity dimension reveals a further gap: governance frameworks that focus on write operations miss a class of tools that expose protected data without modifying state. These sensitive-read tools require the same accountability infrastructure – authentication, logging, attribution – as their state-modifying counterparts. Among servers with such tools, 79% lack co-located audit logging.

These findings land in a moment of active standards convening. The NIST AI Agent Standards Initiative, the CoSAI Agentic Identity and Access Management framework, the CoSAI MCP Security threat taxonomy, and the OWASP MCP Top 10 each prescribe controls for the gaps measured here. None measures whether those controls are adopted in deployment. Recent protocol- and orchestration-layer moves – among them the MCP project’s Enterprise-Managed Authorization and its advancing authorization specification (step-up scope accumulation in SEP-2350 and the forthcoming release candidate, and a rejected per-tool-scope proposal, SEP-1880), emerging vendor agent-identity models (2026), IETF agent-delegation drafts, and a shipping orchestration gateway – are actively standardizing identity, authorization, and multi-hop delegation, but none yet carries published adoption or efficacy evidence, and none closes the server-side actor-attribution gap measured here. This study supplies that empirical baseline, against which the prescriptive frameworks can now be evaluated. The substrate measured here also defines where individual-server governance ends and multi-agent security (Schroeder de Witt et al. 2026) begins: methods that span composition, delegation, and emergence will require measurement capabilities the single-server pipeline bounds but cannot itself provide.

Grounded in the XACML/ABAC architecture and NIST SP 800-162, six governance concerns frame the ecosystem’s posture: policy authoring, attribute context, policy decision, trust chaining, enforcement, and audit. Of these, enforcement and audit are directly measurable from source code and policy authoring is partially observable through annotation adoption and read/write separation; the remaining three – decision logic, attribute management, and trust propagation – require runtime instrumentation and define the scope for future empirical work as that instrumentation matures. The ecosystem is strongest at enforcement (81% authentication) and weakest at audit (17% actor attribution). The individual standards for closing this gap exist – OAuth 2.0 Token Exchange (RFC 8693) with `sub` and `act.sub` claims for actor attribution, SPIFFE for workload identity, OpenTelemetry for correlation, hash-chaining (RFC 4998) for tamper evidence. Their composition into continuous multi-hop trust chains is now under active standardization; what remains unmeasured – and what this study supplies the method to measure – is whether that composition is adopted in deployment.

Agent governance becomes meaningful when implementation evidence catches up to framework prescription. The empirical surface for that evidence now exists. The work is no longer to imagine the controls; it is to measure them, and to verify whether the standards now being composed for that gap (on the wire and in deployment) actually close it.

Data Availability Statement

The analysis instrument, canonical population snapshot, sample draws, evidence corpus, LLM verification results, and human validation data are available as supplementary materials. The data — canonical population snapshot, sample draws, evidence corpus, and LLM verification outputs — is archived on Zenodo (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20970604). The reproduction code (analysis scripts that regenerate every reported number, the LLM verification prompts, and the human validation samples) is available in the public GitHub repository, and the analysis instrument is published as the `cc-mcp-audit` npm package. The reproduction package includes exact steps to regenerate all findings from the population snapshot.

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